

FACTORS AFFECTING STARTUP INTENTIONS OF STUDENTS IN VIETNAM CASE IN HO CHI MINH CITY

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Abstract

This research was initiated to investigate the determinants that impact the entrepreneurial intentions of students in Ho Chi Minh City. The exploration of this subject matter equips students with a more nuanced comprehension and an objective perspective regarding the current entrepreneurial intentions prevalent among the student populace, in addition to elucidating the variables that shape these intentions. Consequently, this understanding facilitates the formulation of strategies aimed at fostering the entrepreneurial ethos among students on a national scale, with a specific focus on those in Ho Chi Minh City. The methodological approach involved the dissemination of online survey instruments, yielding a total of 592 completed responses. Upon meticulous examination of the data, 16 responses were deemed invalid due to uniformity in answers. Ultimately, the analysis was based on 575 valid survey responses. The investigation employed linear regression modeling for hypothesis testing. Findings from the research indicate the presence of five significant factors influencing the entrepreneurial intentions of students in Ho Chi Minh City, specifically identified as "Feasibility perception", "Social perception", "Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy", "Available instruments" and "Attitude". Finally, this study offers several managerial implications aimed at motivating the entrepreneurial spirit among *students*.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship; Students; Entrepreneurial Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship functions as a driving force for the evolution of innovation, as it encompasses the methodical approach of transforming knowledge into valuable products and services, in conjunction with efficient marketing strategies (Romano et al., 2001). It generates new opportunities for individuals and enhances their quality of life by offering a diverse array of products and services. Furthermore, entrepreneurship represents a significant element that national policymakers should recognize for its pivotal contributions (Barnir et al., 2011) that span from macroeconomic to microeconomic benefits. Consequently, entrepreneurship remains a focal subject of considerable interest in Vietnam, particularly within the framework of robust national integration, and has attracted both attention and investment from global enterprises. The expected outcomes

of entrepreneurship include fostering economic growth, generating employment opportunities, and addressing the increasingly diverse demands of society. Specifically, the emergence of over 1,800 startup enterprises, alongside 21 incubators and 7 business promotion organizations—including notable entities such as Tiki, Sendo, and Shopee—serves as compelling evidence of the burgeoning entrepreneurial spirit in Vietnam (Ministry of Science and Technology, 2024).

The report entitled "The Landscape of Creative Startups in Vietnam 2019," released by the Australian Trade and Investment Commission, further affirms that Vietnam currently occupies the third position in Southeast Asia concerning the number of startups. Nonetheless, despite the establishment of startup incubators within higher education institutions and the formulation of numerous policies and opportunities aimed at fostering entrepreneurial ventures, statistical data indicates that merely 2-3% of students express a desire to embark on entrepreneurial endeavors (Nga, 2021). Moreover, a survey conducted by the Vietnam Chamber of Commerce and Industry (VCCI) reveals that a staggering 66.6% of Vietnamese students lack awareness regarding entrepreneurial activities. Therefore, to have an objective view of the current student start-up issue as well as to find out the factors affecting students' intention to start-up a business, the authors proposed to research this topic.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Entrepreneurship

Hisrich & Drovensek (2002) conceptualized entrepreneurship as a systematic endeavor aimed at generating novel and valuable entities through the investment of requisite time and effort to attain financial autonomy, which inherently entails financial, emotional, and social uncertainties. In the perspective of Nga & Shamuganathan (2010), entrepreneurship constitutes the active pursuit of economic prospects via individual initiative or innovative concepts within an unpredictable operational framework characterized by limited material resources. In more accessible terms, this investigation will characterize entrepreneurship as the inception of a new business or the formation of a novel enterprise through inventive business concepts, along with the identification and utilization of opportunities to derive fulfillment from one's own business (Koe et al., 2012), while the entrepreneur must demonstrate a willingness to embrace risks associated with change and proactively capitalize on opportunities to generate additional value (Shane, 2012).

Indeed, the element of risk is an omnipresent aspect that invariably accompanies the narrative of entrepreneurship and is evident in requisite innovations (Setiawan, 2014). The efforts of assuming risks to pursue innovation within the business domain, thereby addressing the continually evolving and limitless demands of individuals and society, epitomizes the essence of entrepreneurship; thus, it is not inappropriate to assert that entrepreneurship ought to be regarded as the "art" of navigating the process of entrepreneurial management to foster autonomy and enhance adaptability, ultimately generating artistic value for both the economy and society (Chang, 2015).

In terms of specific scholarly inquiry, entrepreneurship currently garners the attention of numerous authors who investigate the phenomenon within various national contexts to cultivate a deeper understanding of entrepreneurship, specifically:

- Research by Sheperd & Krueger (2002) has expanded the definition that an entrepreneur's self-efficacy will influence the entrepreneur's choice of action and determine their energy consumption (or effort) in the process of achieving their goals.
- Research conducted by Salwah Che Mat et al. (2015). In 2015, the investigation by them in Indonesia formulated a model elucidating students' entrepreneurial intention. This model posits four determinants: *Locus of control, need for achievement, subjective norms, and available instruments*. The authors contend that internal sentiments will facilitate individuals in formulating thoughts, and orientations regarding issues, as well as selecting appropriate behaviors. Subjective norms are personal perceptions recognized as a crucial determinant of behavior, thereby illuminating and acknowledging one's inherent need for achievement.
- Research by Syed Ali Raza, Wasim Qazi & Nida Shah (2018). This study scrutinizes the variables influencing the motivation and intention to embark on an entrepreneurial journey among students at the University of Business. The findings indicate that subjective norms, opportunities, attitudes, perceived behavioral control, motivation, and personal capability exert a positive influence on the entrepreneurial intentions of students at the University of Business.
- Research by Nguyen X.H et al. (2018). The investigation into the factors influencing the entrepreneurial intentions of Economics students at universities in Ho Chi Minh City is predicated on Ajzen's theory of planned behavior (TPB) (1991). The attitude towards entrepreneurial behavior, as articulated by Luthje & Franke (2003), is elucidated through the need for achievement, the propensity to embrace risks, and the internal locus of control (collectively termed personality traits); or, according to Karali (2013), through the business education curriculum.
- Research by Huynh N.N et al. (2020). The research results show that the ability factor greatly affects students' intention to start a business. When students feel that they are not competent enough, they will lack the confidence to start a business. Enhancing students' perception, attitude, and motivation to start a business through regular extracurricular activities or organizing business idea competitions.

2.2 Entrepreneurial intention

Various scholarly analyses have highlighted entrepreneurial intention as a fundamental determinant of entrepreneurial engagement and actions (Autio et al., 2001). It can be asserted that the forecasting of entrepreneurial activity and behavior has been affirmed as significant and positively correlated with the nexus between entrepreneurial intention and entrepreneurial engagement from a formative age. The fundamental justification for the increased significance of entrepreneurial intention, as previously discussed, was articulated by Thompson (2009), who proposed that it relates to beliefs; specifically, as levels of belief intensify, entrepreneurial intention correspondingly rises because intention

is characterized as "an individual's self-awareness of the belief that he seeks to establish a new business initiative and has a purposeful plan to accomplish this at a future time." Consequently, entrepreneurial intention will serve as an indicator of an individual's preparedness, aspiration, and planning to embark on entrepreneurship, leading them to regard it as a viable career path and to partake in entrepreneurial endeavors (Alammari et al., 2019).

3. HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT AND MODEL

3.1 Available instruments

Access to financial resources, relevant information, and social networks are deemed to significantly affect entrepreneurial intention. These three elements are categorized as available instruments. According to Mazzarol et al (1999), capital is defined as an economic attribute or characteristic. In the context of this study, capital is conceptualized as monetary resources allocated for entrepreneurial efforts. Such capital may derive from various sources, including familial support, loans, personal savings, or alternative means. As posited by Zain et al. (2010), a model explaining the factors influencing students' entrepreneurial intention was developed, which encompassed the variable of capital; the findings indicated a positive correlation between capital and entrepreneurial intention.

Access to information pertains to an entrepreneur's capacity to acquire knowledge that aids in the attainment of business objectives or the resolution of business challenges. Singh & Krishna (1994) articulated that a strong intention for information access constitutes one of the primary criteria among Indian entrepreneurs. The process of information retrieval may contain the exploration of projects, opportunities, financial resources, and market analysis. Entrepreneurs engage in communication not only with individuals within their organizations but also with external parties. Social networking serves as a critical business instrument that significantly influences entrepreneurial success. Entrepreneurs must cultivate strong social and personal connections as a supportive framework for their enterprises. Azahari et al. (2013) admitted that networking is vital for entrepreneurs to obtain access to intangible resources, whether directly or indirectly.

Based on the preceding hypotheses, the authors posit the following hypothesis H1:

Hypothesis H1: *Available instruments have a positive influence on entrepreneurial intentions.*

3.2 Attitude (towards entrepreneurship)

The concept of attitude towards a specific behavior pertains to the degree to which an individual holds either favorable or unfavorable assessments regarding the behavior under consideration (Ajzen, 1991). According to Krueger et al. (2000), attitude is characterized as a persistent framework of affirmative or negative evaluations concerning a particular object. This concept encapsulates the manner in which an individual appraises and contrasts an object against available alternatives, based on the individual's cognitive processes (thoughts), belief systems (values), and emotional responses

(effectives) pertaining to the object. Similarly, Mumtaz et al. (2012) discovered that the attitudes of university students found a constructive influence on their entrepreneurial intentions. In summary, a positive attitude among students is likely to yield numerous beneficial outcomes in reinforcing an individual's resolve to pursue entrepreneurship (Khoi, Hai & Long, 2021).

Based on the aforementioned hypotheses, the authors posit hypothesis H2 as follows:

Hypothesis H2: *The attitude (towards entrepreneurship) has a positive influence on entrepreneurial intentions.*

3.3 Entrepreneurial self-efficacy

Personal competencies encompass the possession of knowledge and skills require for the execution of any given task. The authors indicated that individuals exhibiting high levels of self-competence and skill sets are significantly more inclined to embark upon entrepreneurial ventures. McMullen & Shepherd (2006) concluded that when entrepreneurs possess the capacity to engage in novel business domains, they are adept at capitalizing on emergent opportunities. The proficiency to identify new opportunities is pivotal for entrepreneurial success (Kara et al., 2010). The transition into entrepreneurship is fundamentally a cognitive undertaking, wherein abilities and skills are instrumental in facilitating this complex process (Bayon et al., 2015). Consequently, the investigation of self-efficacy is of paramount importance for comprehending individual behavior, as it can significantly influence a person's persistence, resilience, and commitment in the face of problem-solving challenges, as well as the extent of effort that an individual is willing to pursue in the pursuit of entrepreneurial endeavors (Memo, Soomro & Shah, 2019).

Based the aforementioned hypotheses, the authors posit the following hypothesis H3:

Hypothesis H3: *Entrepreneurial self-efficacy has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial intentions.*

3.4 Social perception

Any individual or organization must operate within a specific contextual framework influenced by temporal, spatial, and situational factors. This contextual framework serves as a determinant that exerts either beneficial or detrimental effects on the individuals and organizations within it. Human behaviors are directed and inspired by social contexts, institutional regulations, and cultural norms.

Based on Nwankwo et al. (2012) and the assumptions that the business process is consciously participated by individuals, theories have been developed to explain what motivates an individual to participate in this process. Clearly, the value of recognizing entrepreneurial culture, along with an insight into the support and collaboration from social stakeholders, will create a sustainable underpinning for developing a resilient and persistent entrepreneurial ecosystem (Bischoff, 2021).

Based the aforementioned hypotheses, the authors posit the following hypothesis H4:

Hypothesis H4: *Social perception has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial intentions.*

3.5 Feasibility perception

Feasibility perception is conceptualized as an individual's assessment regarding the simplicity or complexity associated with executing a specific behavior; additionally, it encompasses the extent to which the execution of such behavior is subject to control or constraints. Feasibility perception relates to the level at which an individual views the initiation of a business initiative as practical (Liñán, 2004). Indeed, the aspiration to establish a business is invariably coupled with the viability of the underlying business concept. As a result, when a concept is perceived as impractical, the impetus to bring it to fruition will wane or evaporate. Consequently, when considering the commencement of a business venture, an individual must dedicate all accessible resources towards implementing an action designed to achieve the established goal, despite the potential obstacles that may emerge (Hoang, 2014). Numerous entrepreneurial concepts have been dismissed due to their infeasibility and the complexities associated with their realization; furthermore, it is imperative to note that a startup concept may be unviable due to its limited efficiency. Thus, feasibility perception instills optimism in the concept, fostering a commitment to engage in entrepreneurial activities; particularly, feasibility perception has a direct influence on behavioral intentions (Ambad & Damit, 2016). In a recent study undertaken by Eysel & Durmaz (2019), the researchers identified that feasibility perception emerged as the primary factor positively influencing entrepreneurial intentions. In light of the aforementioned propositions, the research team formulated hypothesis H5 as follows:

Hypothesis H5: *Feasibility perception has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial intentions.*

3.6 Conceptual model

Figure 1: Conceptual model (Source: Authors)

Hypothesis H1: *Available instruments (AI) have a positive influence on entrepreneurial intentions.*

Hypothesis H2: *The attitude (AT) (towards entrepreneurship) has a positive influence on entrepreneurial intentions.*

Hypothesis H3: *Entrepreneurial self-efficacy (ES) has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial intentions.*

Hypothesis H4: *Social perception (SP) has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial intentions.*

Hypothesis H5: *Feasibility perception (FP) has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial intentions.*

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Cronbach's alpha analysis

In the reliability analysis phase, the author assessed all six variables, which comprised 05 independent variables and 01 dependent variable, using Likert's scale. The findings from the reliability assessments for each variable are summarized in Table 1 below.

Then, 04 observed variables within three independent scales failed to meet the reliability criteria and were subsequently excluded: AI1, AI2, SP5, and FP6.

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha of Factors

Factor	Observed variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Available instruments (AI)	AI3, AI4, AI5, AI6, AI7, AI8	0.788
Attitude (AT)	AT1, AT2, AT3, AT4, AT5	0.698
Entrepreneurial self-efficacy (ES)	ES1, ES2, ES3, ES4, ES5	0.721
Social perception (SP)	SP1, SP2, SP3, SP4	0.776
Feasibility perception (FP)	EP1, EP2, EP3, EP4, EP5	0.735
Entrepreneurial intentions (EI)	EI1, EI2, EI3, EI4, EI5, EI6	0.679

Source: Authors

The measurement results for the six component scales, which include 05 independent variables and 01 dependent variable, meet the requirements with a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient when they are all greater than 0.6. Additionally, all observed variables within the component scales have a correlation coefficient with the total greater than 0.3.

So, this indicates that the constructed scales are statistically meaningful and have achieved the necessary reliability, allowing them to proceed to Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). The assessment of the scales confirms that they all meet the reliability criteria as evaluated by Cronbach's Alpha.

Therefore, the model comprises 25 independent observed variables and 6 dependent observed variables, which will be included in the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA).

4.2 Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

The Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted using SPSS version 20.0. The EFA results show that the KMO index is 0.884, exceeding the threshold of 0.5, and the significance value from Bartlett's test is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Those results indicate that the variables are correlated, making the model suitable for Exploratory Factor Analysis.

All five factors were extracted, each having a corresponding eigenvalue greater than 1, with the fifth factor showing an eigenvalue of 1.025 (which is also greater than 1).

The total variance explained by the 05 factors is 59.691%, indicating that these 05 components account for 59.691% of the variance in the observed variables.

Based on the final factor rotation matrix from the EFA, 05 factors were successfully extracted.

Then there were only 18 observed variables left and were divided into 05 groups as follows in the table 2:

Table 2: Result of Exploratory Factor Analysis

Variances	Factor Loading				
	1	2	3	4	5
AI3	.742				
AI4	.735				
AI6	.686				
AI5	.677				
AI7	.595				
SP2		.775			
SP3		.747			
SP1		.691			
SP4		.635			
ES2			.735		
ES5			.705		
ES1			.692		
ES4			.588		
FP4				.788	
FP5				.699	
FP2				.665	
AT2					.842
AT1					.836

Source: Authors

The author's final results are presented as follows:

- Factor 1: Comprising the observed variables AI3, AI4, AI5, AI6, and AI7, which are part of the initial scale measuring “Available instruments” that is coded as **AI**
- Factor 2: Comprising the observed variables SP1, SP2, SP3, and SP4 from the initial scale measuring “Social Perception” this factor is coded as **SP**

- Factor 3: Comprising the observed variables ES1, ES2, ES4, and ES5 from the initial scale measuring “Entrepreneurial self-efficacy” this factor is coded as **ES**
- Factor 4: Comprising the observed variables FP2, FP4, and FP5 from the initial scale measuring “Feasibility Perception” this factor is coded as **FP**
- Factor 5: Comprising the observed variables AT1 and AT2 from the initial scale measuring “Attitude,” this factor is coded as **AT**

4.3 Regression Analysis

The adjusted R² value is 0.580, indicating that the independent variables in the model can explain 58% of the variance in the dependent variable. In other words, this adjusted R² reflects that 58% of the model's suitability is accounted for, while the remaining variation is attributed to error and other factors. The Durbin-Watson statistic is 1.653, which falls within the range of [1 < D < 3], suggesting that there is no evidence of correlation among the residuals (See table 3 below)

Table 3: Model summary table

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.764 ^a	.584	.580	.47122	1.653
a. Predictors: AI, SP, ES, FP, AT					
b. Dependent Variable: EI					

When examining the conditions for the independent variables AI, SP, ES, FP and AT, all met the required criteria, as indicated by the significance values (Sig.) which were all below 0.05, demonstrating a high level of reliability. Additionally, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for all Beta coefficients was below 10, and the Tolerance values were above 0.5, indicating that there is no multicollinearity present.

Table 4: Statistical parameters of regression model

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	.408	.115		3.553	.000		
	AI	.170	.032	.177	5.319	.000	.664	1.507
	SP	.201	.031	.222	6.466	.000	.620	1.612
	ES	.206	.032	.214	6.419	.000	.658	1.520
	FP	.342	.030	.371	11.456	.000	.698	1.432
	AT	.007	.023	.009	3.304	.000	.858	1.165

a. Dependent Variable: EI

The multiple linear regression equation is as follows:

$$\text{Entrepreneurial Intention (EI)} = 0.177 \cdot \text{Available instruments (AI)} + 0.222 \cdot \text{Social Perception (SP)} + 0.214 \cdot \text{Entrepreneurial self-efficacy (ES)} + 0.371 \cdot \text{Feasibility Perception (FP)} + 0.009 \cdot \text{Attitude (AT)}$$

Results presented in table 4 show that all five factors (AI, SP, ES, FP, AT) have a positive influence on Entrepreneurial Intention (EI). Notably, the factor of **Feasibility perception**

has the most significant impact (Beta = 0.371), followed by **Social perception** (Beta = 0.222), **Entrepreneurial self-efficacy** (Beta = 0.214), **Available instruments** (Beta=0.177), while **Attitude** has the least influence (Beta = 0.009).

5. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Based on empirical research findings, this paper provides management implications aimed at enhancing universities' understanding of the significance of fostering a start-up spirit in students' entrepreneurial intentions. This, in turn, can enable universities to establish more supportive conditions to assist students in their entrepreneurial pursuits.

• Feasibility Perception:

The perception of feasibility constitutes the fundamental basis, instilling a sense of security and confidence among individuals contemplating the initiation of a business venture. Academic institutions must duly consider the incorporation of entrepreneurship education and formulate strategic plans to support topics that are both persuasive and eminently feasible. The significance and efficacy of entrepreneurship education in fostering economic development have been acknowledged in the majority of developed nations (Garba, 2010). Consequently, universities ought to perceive education not merely as the dissemination of knowledge but also as the provision of additional resources that bolster confidence, thereby enhancing the propensity to embark on entrepreneurial endeavors. It is imperative to influence perceptions from within, enabling students to recognize the advantages associated with entrepreneurship and business activities through highly practical and relatable avenues, such as personal enrichment, familial support, financial autonomy to fulfill individual needs and aspirations, community assistance, and contributions to the advancement of a prosperous and robust nation. Policymakers are urged to design a greater number of seminars and events centered on the introduction of startups, while simultaneously offering foundational knowledge on financial management and business initiation, allowing students to gradually assimilate and become more familiar with the concept of startups, thus elevating their awareness and self-assurance. Students should engage in knowledge exchange with peers and educators who possess practical experience. In addition to imparting theoretical knowledge, educational institutions must concentrate on developing pragmatic lessons and scenarios that closely mirror real-world situations, thereby affording students the opportunity to engage in hands-on practice during the learning process, fostering their motivation and instilling a strong conviction in the feasibility of startups, ultimately enabling them to identify opportunities, secure economic resources, and enhance their capacity to manage and cultivate successful projects.

• Social perception:

The influence exerted by family, friends, and all individuals who facilitate and endorse an entrepreneur's initiatives significantly shapes the cognitive processes, perceptions, and behaviors of that individual in their deliberation on the commencement of a business venture. Consequently, to bolster students' entrepreneurial aspirations, it is imperative that family members and friends serve as unwavering and robust pillars of support for the

individual contemplating the initiation of a business endeavor. The collaborative assistance and contributions rendered by educational institutions, familial units, and policymakers play a crucial role. Educational institutions are tasked with imparting fundamental and lucid knowledge regarding the initiation of a business, thereby equipping students with a thorough understanding that mitigates any potential uncertainties associated with entrepreneurship. Families must actively foster and inspire students harboring entrepreneurial intentions, as such intentions often indicate a burgeoning awareness of their inherent capabilities and attributes. The familial encouragement serves to augment the students' self-efficacy and confidence in their entrepreneurial pursuits. Furthermore, policymakers are urged to formulate and implement additional supportive policies that cater specifically to students aspiring to embark on entrepreneurial ventures.

- **Entrepreneurial self-efficacy:**

Selecting an appropriate domain that aligns with individual strengths for the initiation of a business necessitates prior experience within that sector to amass relevant knowledge, practical experience, and essential competencies. This undertaking is time-intensive yet constitutes a crucial phase in the entrepreneurial journey. The possession of soft skills is regarded as a critical determinant of success. While soft skills may not possess definitive importance in determining the outcome of a business venture, they serve as an auxiliary element that enhances the likelihood of success during the startup process and establishes a proactive stance for the enterprise in the face of potential challenges. It is essential to fortify the collaborative relationship between entrepreneurs and academic institutions, fostering a more integrated partnership. The methodologies or business models employed by entrepreneurs contribute significantly to the enhancement of knowledge. Moreover, educational institutions and businesses should facilitate exchanges to enable students to gain insight into their capabilities and strive for self-improvement. Incentive structures for scholarships should be advocated to identify talent and cultivate both professional knowledge and soft skills, while simultaneously promoting an entrepreneurial mindset.

- **Available instruments:**

The findings of the research indicate that the variable of available instruments significantly influences students' motivations to embark on entrepreneurial ventures. Consequently, it is imperative to enhance the accessibility of resources for students. Students must possess a comprehensive understanding of the substantial potential inherent in information and social networks. These platforms serve not merely as sources of entertainment but also as robust assets, provided they are adeptly harnessed and fully utilized. Furthermore, in the context of initiating a business, a degree of naivety is unavoidable; thus, the accumulation of knowledge pertaining to market dynamics, competitive products, and methodologies for product introduction is directly correlated with the likelihood of market infiltration. Continuous self-improvement is essential and must be pursued relentlessly. The Ministry of Education and Training actively fosters an entrepreneurial ethos among learners, facilitating a transformation in students' cognitive

frameworks, perceptions, and aspirations, thereby empowering them to actualize their innovative concepts. The Ministry of Education and Training collaborates with the Ministry of Finance and other pertinent agencies to formulate policies that nurture the nation's human capital. Additionally, financial and credit institutions are encouraged to pay increased attention to nascent initiatives and to proactively support viable business concepts proposed by students. It is crucial to refine the mechanisms and methodologies for capital provision to ensure the stability of banking and credit institutions while concurrently enabling students to develop robust and effective business projects.

6. LIMITATIONS AND PROPOSED DIRECTIONS OF THE RESEARCH

The article has elucidated the findings regarding the affirmative influence of all five factors on students' entrepreneurial intentions. Consequently, the author has also delineated implications derived from the aforementioned factors, aspiring to enhance the cultivation of students' entrepreneurial aspirations. Nevertheless, there exist certain limitations that warrant attention and may be leveraged in subsequent researches:

- This investigation may be augmented by incorporating additional variables to attain a more comprehensive understanding of other determinants that could influence students' entrepreneurial intentions, such as technological influences and familial background factors.
- This analysis presently concentrates solely on the youth demographic comprising university students within a specific locale, thereby constraining the observation of significant variances. Therefore, future research endeavors could be pursued in alternative regions or international contexts. This approach would serve to enrich the findings of the study.

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